

FACTORS INFLUENCING STUDENT'S ENGAGEMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IKENNE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study assessed factors influencing students' engagement in public secondary schools in Ikenne Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria.

The population comprised of SS3 students in Ikenne LGA. A simple random technique was used to select 322 respondents from the selected schools. Student School Engagement Questionnaire (SSEQ) and School Engagement Factors Questionnaire (SEFQ) was used to obtain data on level of students' engagement, personal factor, parental involvement factor and school factors. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypothesis.

Result showed that students are engaged in different school engagement factors that facilitates student engagement in classroom with a mean score for personal factors ($m = 3.46$, $SD = .743$); school environment ($m = 2.91$, $SD = 0.889$); teaching method ($m = 3.45$, $SD = 0.758$); technology use ($m = 3.52$, $SD = 0.898$); student teacher relationship ($m = 3.19$, $SD = 0.711$) and Parental Involvement ($m = 3.52$, $SD = 0.747$). PPMC analysis shows that there is a positive significant relationship between personal factors ($r = .135$, $p < 0.05$) and school factors ($r = .137$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that school engagement factors significantly predict students' engagement toward learning. Recommendations were made for improvement of students' engagement in schools.

Introduction

Student engagement plays a vital part in academic success, significantly influencing not only academic success and achievement but also the emotional intelligence outcomes for students. Research has shown that engaged students are more likely to excel academically and experience enhanced social and emotional well-being (Pedler *et al.*, 2020). Although the notion of student engagement is interwoven, Christenson, Reschly, and Wylie (2012) described student engagement as the active involvement and dedication of students to their learning objectives. Moreover, various factors can affect the level of student engagement, including individual characteristics, parental involvement or concern about child's education, the school environment, teaching strategies employed by teachers, technological factors and students-teacher relationship.

For instance, personal factors which encompasses students' behaviors' such as participation and punctuality play an essential role in student engagement. Also, emotions which includes interest, motivation, or attitude whether positive or negative can affect the student willingness to engage in classroom. Similarly, awareness which involve students' strengths, weaknesses and their learning needs are important factors that interact and actively determines students' engagement. Sokmen (2021) noted that students who possess high self-efficacy and motivation which are indicators of personal factors that can affect students' engagement in classroom tend to be more engaged in their learning experiences.

Similarly, parental involvement is another critical factor in promoting student engagement. This is because parents have a substantial impact on their children's educational journey and motivation, and are often the foundation layers, contributing to positive engagement outcomes and academic success (Mose and Villodas, 2017). Yu, Gao, and Wang (2021) also noted that supportive school environment that emphasizes social support, freedom, a sense of competence, and teacher support is essential for fostering student engagement. This also includes integrating technology into lessons such as online discussions, creative presentations, and educational games can significantly boost students' motivation and involvement.

Furthermore, variable such as teaching methods are crucial in fostering student engagement, as the manner in which educators deliver instruction greatly influences students' motivation, participation, and overall learning experiences. Specifically, interactive teaching techniques, including discussions, group work, and hands-on activities, are particularly effective in enhancing student engagement (Gute and Wainman, 2019). Additionally, Wang *et al.*, (2020) found out that cultivating positive student-teacher relationships leads to increased engagement, motivation, and academic success.

It is evident that student engagement is a vital aspect of academic excellence which encompasses emotional and behavioral involvement as it significantly influences motivation, learning and overall educational experience. Despite the importance of students' engagement in achieving academic success and positive educational outcomes, public secondary schools in Ikenne LGA are faced with the challenge of low student engagement, manifesting in poor academic performance. This situation is exacerbated by lack of empirical evidence on the factors that influence student engagement in these schools, making it difficult for educators and policy makers to develop effective strategies to promote student engagement. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the factors affecting students' engagement within public secondary schools in Ikenne Local Government Area.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey design.

Population of the study

The population used for the study comprised of SS3 students in Ikenne Local Government Area in Ogun State. The total population was 1,652 students.

Sampling Size and Technique

Using proportionate random sampling technique, five schools were selected from eleven schools across the towns in the LGA. Taro Yamane's (1974) formula was used to arrive at the sample size for the selected secondary schools.

Taro Yamane's (1974) formula ($n =$), where: n = Sample size (to be calculated);

N = Population of the study area (1,652)

e = level of precision = 0.05. Hence, 322 sample size was generated.

S/N	School	SS3 Student's Population
1	Ilishan High School, Ilishan Remo	283
2	Christ Apostolic Grammar School, Iperu Remo	357
3	Mayflower School, Ikenne Remo	519
4	Ositelu Memorial College, Ogere	262
5	Irolu Community High School, Irolu	231
	Total	1,652 = (322)

Since the population sample of each school differs, proportionate sampling technique was employed to draw out appropriate sample size for each school using the formula:

$$(Sample\ size\ for\ each\ school = \frac{Total\ sample\ size * School's\ population}{Total\ population})$$

S/N	School	SS3 Student's Population	
1	Ilishan High School, Ilishan Remo	283	55
2	Christ Apostolic Grammar School, Iperu Remo	357	70

3	Mayflower School, Ikenne Remo	519	101
4	Ositelu Memorial College, Ogere	262	51
5	Irolu Community High School, Irolu	231	45
	Total	1,652	322

Simple random technique was used to select 322 respondents from the selected schools.

Research Instrument and Reliability

A two-parts questionnaire Student School Engagement Questionnaire (SSEQ) and School Engagement Factors Questionnaire (SEFQ) measuring personal Factors, parental involvement factors, school factors (school environment, teaching method, technology and use of technology) was used to gather data for the study. SSEQ had a reliability coefficient of .795. Meanwhile, SEFQ had a reliability coefficient of .786, .871, .967, .954, .852, and .793.

Method of Data Collection

Primary data was gathered through the dissemination of questionnaires.

Method of Data Analysis

Data gathered was analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean. Mean values greater than or equal to 2.55 equals agree while those below 2.55 are disagree. Hypothesis was analyzed using Pearson Moment Correlation Test (PPMC).

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What is the level of students’ engagement in public secondary schools in Ikenne Local Government Area?

Table 1: Students School Engagement

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean (m)	Standard Deviation (SD)
I work hard to perform well academically	44 (13.7)	48 (14.9)	45 (14.0)	185 (57.5)	3.15	1.118
I put in my best effort in class	44 (13.7)	42(13.0)	55 (17.1)	181 (56.2)	3.16	1.104

I also actively participate in class discussions at school	41 (12.7)	96 (29.8)	85 (26.4)	100 (31.1)	2.76	1.031
In class, I listen to what my teachers are saying	53 (16.5)	80 (24.8)	90 (28.0)	99 (30.7)	2.73	1.070
Grand Mean					2.95	1.080

The results from Table 1 show grand mean scores on engagement ($m = 2.95$, $SD = 1.080$). The grand mean shows that the respondents agree on the student's engagement parameters. Meanwhile, the respondents agreed that they work hard to perform well academically ($m = 3.15$, $SD = 1.118$); put in their best effort in class ($m = 3.16$, $SD = 1.104$); actively participate in class discussions at school ($m = 2.76$, $SD = 1.031$); and listen to what their teachers say ($m = 2.73$, $SD = 1.070$).

Research Question Two: What are the personal factors in public secondary schools in Ikenne local government area?

Table 2: Students Personal Factors

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean (m)	Standard Deviation (SD)
I have a strong desire to succeed academically	11 (3.4)	30 (9.3)	120 (37.3)	161 (50.0)	3.34	.786
I make myself objectives and strive to meet them	3 (0.9)	24 (7.5)	102 (31.7)	193 (59.9)	3.51	.676
My current subjects meet my curiosity	1 (0.3)	33 (10.2)	111 (34.5)	177 (55.0)	3.44	.687
I think my academic endeavors will pay off in the long run	9 (2.8)	42 (13.0)	30 (9.3)	241 (74.8)	3.56	.823
Grand Mean					3.46	.743

The results of Table 2 show a grand mean score for personal factors ($m = 3.46, SD = .743$). This implies that the respondents agreed on the personal factor's parameters and that their personal factors have an influence on their engagement in school. Meanwhile, the respondents maintained that they have a strong desire to succeed academically ($m = 3.34, SD = .786$); they make personal objectives and strive to meet them ($m = 3.51, SD = .676$); their current subjects meet their curiosity ($m = 3.44, SD = .687$); and believe their academic endeavors will pay off in long run ($m = 3.56, SD = .823$).

Research Question Three: What are the school factors (school environment, teaching methods, teacher students' relationship, use of technology) in public secondary schools in Ikenne local government area?

Table 3: School Engagement Factors

A. School Environment

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean (m)	Standard Deviation (SD)
The school's classrooms are roomy and equipped with sufficient supplies	13 (4.0)	31 (9.6)	43 (13.4)	235 (73.0)	3.30	1.070
The school is equipped with well-equipped labs	35 (10.9)	45 (14.0)	31 (9.6)	211 (65.5)	3.55	.827
There are enough reference books in the school library	12 (3.7)	203 (63.0)	56 (17.4)	51 (15.8)	2.45	.801
There are enough well-ventilated classrooms at the school, and there are sufficient medical facilities	13 (4.0)	179 (55.6)	64 (19.9)	66 (20.5)	2.57	.859
Grand Mean					2.91	0.889

The results of Table 3 show a grand mean score for School Environment factors ($m = 2.91, SD = .889$). This implies that the respondents agreed that school environment affects school engagement. Meanwhile, results shows that classrooms are roomy and equipped with sufficient supplies environment have an influence on their engagement in school ($m = 3.30, SD = 1.070$); the school is equipped with well-

equipped labs ($m = 3.55$, $SD = .827$); there are enough reference books in the school library ($m = 2.45$, $SD = .801$); and there are enough well-ventilated classrooms at school and there are sufficient medical facilities ($m = 2.57$, $SD = .859$).

B. Teaching Method

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean (m)	Standard Deviation (SD)
We participate in self-directed learning activities with our teachers	6 (1.9)	34 (10.6)	85 (26.4)	197 (61.2)	3.47	.757
Teachers engage us in class discussions	4 (1.2)	40 (12.4)	81 (25.2)	156 (48.4)	3.34	.783
At the conclusion of each lesson, teachers give students questions to answer	5 (1.6)	47 (14.6)	102 (31.7)	168 (52.2)	3.46	.757
Teachers let us talk to each other in class while we're learning	7 (2.2)	26 (8.1)	72 (22.4)	217 (67.4)	3.55	.736
Grand Mean					3.45	0.758

The results from table above shows a grand mean score for teaching method ($m = 3.45$, $SD = .758$). This implies that the respondents agreed with the teaching method parameters. Meanwhile, the respondents maintain that they participate in self-directed learning activities with their teachers ($m = 3.47$, $SD = .757$); teachers engage them in class discussions ($m = 3.34$, $SD = .783$); at the conclusion of each lesson, teachers give students questions to answer ($m = 3.46$, $SD = .757$); and teachers let them talk to each other in class while they are learning ($m = 3.55$, $SD = .736$).

C. Student Teacher Relationship

Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean (m)	Standard Deviation
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	(<i>n</i>)				(<i>SD</i>)	
Teachers work hard to improve student performance	26 (8.1)	31 (9.6)	106 (32.9)	159 (49.4)	3.14	.534
Teachers use their free time to assist students in improving their grades	5 (1.6)	20 (6.2)	127 (39.4)	170 (52.8)	2.98	.703
Teachers are supportive and available to assist students with their academic needs at any time	10 (3.1)	53 (16.5)	193 (59.9)	66 (20.5)	3.43	.682
Teachers encourage their students to consider their future aspirations	5 (1.6)	11 (3.4)	239 (74.2)	67 (20.8)	3.24	.927
Grand Mean					3.19	0.711

The results from table above shows a grand mean score for student teacher relationship ($m = 3.19$, $SD = .711$). This shows that the respondents agreed that student teacher relationship matters in school engagement. Also, the respondents maintain that teachers work hard to improve student performance ($m = 3.14$, $SD = .534$); teachers use their free time to assist students in improving their grade ($m = 2.98$, $SD = .703$); teachers are supportive and available to assist students with their academic needs at any time ($m = 3.43$, $SD = .682$); and teachers encourage their students to consider their future aspirations ($m = 3.24$, $SD = .927$).

D. Use of Technology

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean (<i>m</i>)	Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)
I enjoy classes where technology is incorporated more than traditional setting class	21 (6.5)	41 (12.7)	56 (17.4)	204 (63.4)	3.38	.940
I retain information more when my teacher uses technology related tools	14 (4.3)	5 (1.6)	57 (17.7)	246 (76.4)	3.41	.804

Technology use in class improves my educational experiences	2 (0.6)	97 (30.1)	73 (22.7)	150 (46.6)	3.15	.878
Technology use in various subjects taught is needed in our school	18 (5.6)	84 (26.1)	70 (21.7)	150 (46.6)	3.09	.972
Grand Mean					3.25	0.898

The results from table above shows a grand mean score for use of technology ($m = 3.25$, $SD = .898$). This implies that the respondents agreed that technology use affects school engagement. Meanwhile, the respondents maintain that they enjoy classes where technology is incorporated more than traditional setting class ($m = 3.38$, $SD = .940$); they retain information more when my teacher uses technology related tools ($m = 3.41$, $SD = .804$); technology use in class improves their educational experiences $m = 3.15$, $SD = .878$); and technology use in various subjects taught is needed in our school ($m = 3.09$, $SD = .972$).

Research Question Four: What is the level of parental involvement in the education of students in public secondary schools in Ikenne Local Government Area?

Table 4: Level of Parental Involvement

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean (m)	Standard Deviation (SD)
I feel more encouraged when supported by my parents as regards my education	3 (0.9)	56 (17.4)	54 (16.8)	209 (64.9)	3.46	.809
My parents involvement gives me a push forward in my education	3 (0.9)	38 (11.8)	52 (16.1)	229 (71.1)	3.57	.734
Involvement of my parents help me to learn even outside school	7 (2.2)	39 (12.1)	77 (23.9)	199 (61.8)	3.45	.789

My parents' empathy gives me more confidence	1 (0.3)	29 (9.0)	60 (18.6)	232 (72.0)	3.62	.659
Grand Mean					3.52	0.747

The results of Table 4 show a grand mean score for parental Involvement ($m = 3.52, SD = 0.747$). This implies that parental factors are important on students' engagement in school. The result also shows that students feel more encouraged when supported by their parents as regards their education ($m = 3.46, SD = .809$); parents involvement gives them a push forward in their education ($m = 3.57, SD = .734$); their parents involvement helps them to learn even outside school ($m = 3.45, SD = .789$); and their parents empathy gives them more confidence ($m = 3.62, SD = .659$).

Hypothesis of the study

H₀: There is no significant relationship between personal factors, school factors, parental involvement and students' engagement in public secondary schools in Ikenne Local Government Area

Table 5: Correlation Analysis of the relationship between personal factors, school factors, parental involvement factors and student engagement in public secondary schools in Ikenne Local

Student Engagement	Personal Factors	Parental Factors	School Factors (School Environment)	Teaching Method	Technology Use	Student Teacher Relationship	Government Area.
1	.251 .000	.209 .000	.176 .024	.028 .611	.057 .304	.061 .279	
.251 .000	1	.213 .000	.079 .158	.135* .016	.049 .383	.032 .568	
.209 .000	.213 .000	1	.193 .001	.084 .134	.050 .372	.084 .132	
.176 .002	.079 .158	.193 .001	1	.095 .088	.137* .014	.187 .001	

.611	.016	.134	.088		.000	.014
.057	.049	.050	.137*	.254	1	.233
.304	.383	.372	.014	.000		.000
.069	.032	.084	.187	.137*	.233	1
.279	.568	.132	.001	.014	.000	

*Correlation is significant at the

0.05 level (2-tailed)

The results showed that there is a significant positive correlation ($r=.135$, $p<0.05$) between personal factors and teaching method. This suggests that students’ personal characteristics are related to their perceptions of the teaching method. The results further showed that there is a significant positive correlation ($r=.137$, $p<0.05$) between school environment and technology use. This indicates that the physical environment of the school is an important factor to the use of technology in the classroom.

Table 5 additionally revealed that there is a significant positive correlation between student-teacher relationship and teaching method ($r=.137$, $p<0.05$). This suggests that the quality of relationship the student and the teacher share is related to the teaching method used by teachers. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of findings

The first finding shows that respondents work hard to perform well academically, put in their best effort in class, actively participate in class discussions at school and listen to what their teachers say. One of the possible reasons for the findings indicating a generally positive agreement on students’ engagement could be their desire to excel academically and achieve educational goals. The result concur with Promethean (2022) who found a significant finding on student engagement. In line with the findings of this study, it submits that engaged students are more likely to be motivated, attentive, and invested in their studies, fostering a conducive environment for effective learning and personal growth.

The second finding revealed that respondents have a strong desire to succeed academically, make personal objectives and strive to meet them, their current subjects meet their curiosity and believe their academic endeavors will pay off in long run. This is in line with Zeng *et al.*, (2020) & Zhang *et al.*, (2020) which revealed that students’ personal emotional engagement such as showing attachments to school, earnestness in the classroom and acquiring positive and negative feelings towards academic and social factors in school are all paramount factors that foster engagement in school.

The third finding revealed that school factors such as school environment, teaching methods, use of technology and teacher students’ relationship have an effect on students’ engagement. This finding is in support of the discovery of Odeh, Angelina & Ezekiel (2015) who outlined that the characteristics of the school environment must include school buildings, furniture’s, playgrounds, sporting facilities and other related equipment which aid the teacher’s delivery of lesson.

These findings demonstrate the effects of school engagement factors in influencing students' engagements. School engagement factors such as Personal factors, parental factors and school environment can greatly impact students' engagement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings made, the study concluded that that school engagement factors significantly predict students' engagement toward learning. Therefore, it is indicated that some factors needs positive consideration so as to improve students' engagement given the importance of students' engagement in their overall academic achievement and success.

From the findings made, it was recommended that :

- To enhance students' engagement in school, the management board of the secondary school need to focus more on school engagement factors such as personal factors, school environment and parental involvement.
- To increase achievement, it is necessary to pay enough and sufficient attention to the personalities of the students, and teachers should be provided with methodological trainings or advice to address this throughout the educational process.

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